

THE GROWTH OF BUY-NOW-PAY-LATER: HOW IT IMPACTS ON SPENDING BEHAVIOR AND FINANCIAL WELL-BEING

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PURPOSE/PROBLEM

Global expenditure is forecast to reach US\$1 trillion globally by 2025 (deHaan et al., 2024). However, BNPL research is still in its infancy. The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of Buy-Now-Pay-Later (BNPL) services on consumer financing and spending behavior. BNPL has seen a significant rise in recent years, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic (Truong & Truong, 2022) with services like Affirm, Klarna, Afterpay and Tencent becoming increasingly popular. These platforms allow consumers to delay payment or split purchases into interest-free installments, often with soft credit checks. BNPL provides consumers with greater flexibility in managing their finances (Bian et al., 2023). Despite these benefits, BNPL also raises important questions about consumer debt and financial stability. The rapid growth of BNPL has led to concerns about how this form of lending may affect consumers' financial well-being, particularly if not managed responsibly (Chandan, 2024). BNPL can exert a profound influence on consumer credit provision and spending behavior. It can boost consumption by making credit more accessible, but its impact on overall consumer financial health is less clear. As it is not regulated under traditional consumer credit law (Johnson et al., 2021). This study aims to explore the following research questions:

1. What impact does BNPL have on consumer spending behavior, whether it leads to impulsive buying?
2. How has impulsive buying and financial self control affected financial well-being?

By examining these questions, this study will provide insights into the effects of BNPL on consumer financing and spending behavior. It will also inform discussions on the appropriate regulatory framework for BNPL services, balancing the

need to protect consumers with the potential benefits of innovation in credit provision.

METHODOLOGY/DESIGN/APPROACH

Several factors influence consumers' intentions to use BNPL services. This study focuses on the below factors and correlation between them:

Perceived ease of use is positively correlated with intentions to use BNPL (M. A. Hidayat & Rudito, n.d.). A study in Indonesia found that certain individuals exhibit hesitancy towards adopting BNPL, highlighting the importance of ease of use and other factors in driving adoption (H. Hidayat et al., 2024). The convenience and ease of use offered by BNPL services can have implications for consumer behavior. BNPL can facilitate impulsive buying and overconsumption, particularly among younger generations. The ease of transacting online can lead to a higher likelihood of making unplanned purchases.

Soft credit check is not hard credit, to approve financing. This means BNPL applications won't hurt your credit score. A soft credit check is a review of your credit profile that doesn't result in a hard inquiry on your credit report. Soft credit checks are often used for pre-approvals and by lenders for BNPL or other types of financing. Unlike hard inquiries, soft inquiries don't impact on your credit score. You can have multiple soft inquiries without any negative effect. To get credit card approval, you must spend a full credit check and take more time to get approvals compared to BNPL process.

Social influence is a significant factor in the adoption and use of BNPL services, particularly among younger generations. The social influence had the strongest impact on the intention to use BNPL on Generation Z (Van Tuan et al., 2024). However, in this research examine the complex interplay of social influence influencing BNPL adoption and consumer behavior with other factors.

Financial self-control refers to an individual's ability to regulate their financial behaviors in alignment with their long-term financial goals. According to (Schombergk et al., 2017), self-control was positively associated with financial well-being, suggesting that individuals with higher levels of self-control tend to make more financially smart decisions. The individuals with lower levels of self-control were more likely to engage in risky financial behaviors (Sekścińska et al., 2021), highlighting the importance of self-control in mitigating impulsive and potentially detrimental financial decisions. However, financial self-control is a critical determinant of financial well-being or not, considering it in correlation with impulsive buying.

Financial well-being means having enough money to live comfortably. It's about feeling good about your money situation and not stressing about it. We can measure financial well-being in different ways. Some common ways include looking at income, spending, debt, savings, and how much debt you have compared to income. However, *Financial well-being* has been studied in various academic fields, including economics, financial counseling and planning, developmental psychology, consumer decision making, and services marketing. However, there is no universally agreed-upon definition or measurement and no clarity regarding its conceptualization and its components. Financial well-being is the perception of being able to sustain current and anticipated desired living standard and financial freedom (Brüggen et al., 2017).

With the above independent and dependent variables. The research model of this study as follows:

H1: Ease of use has positive impact on impulsive buying

H2: Soft credit checks have positively impact on impulsive buying

H3: Social influence has positive impact on impulsive buying

H4: Impulsive buying has negative impact on impulsive buying.

H5: Financial self control has a negative impact on financial well-being.

The study plans to collect data using a questionnaire survey (to be conducted after ATC) with 250 – 300 respondents expected. A seven-point Likert-type scale rang-

ing from 1 (“strongly disagree”) to 7 (“strongly agree”) will be used in the questionnaire. The study will then use Structured Equation Modeling using SPSS to analyze the data collected and test the above hypotheses.

EXPECTED FINDINGS

The impact of BNPL impulsive buying and along with financial self-control impact on personal financial well-being, remains a controversial issue. There is a lack of long-term studies to find determinants that BNPL negatively affects financial well-being. This study aims to contribute to this research area. The impulsive nature of BNPL and the influence of various factors on the degree of impulsiveness are not yet clearly understood and require further investigation. This is crucial for the sustainable development of BNPL services in the future and it is also important to policy makers, marketers, e-commerce, BNPL services providers and retailers.

A limitation of this study is the insufficient longitude to comprehensively research whether impulsiveness truly impacts well-being is needed to further research. Another thing, we collect data from Vietnam market only and the sample size is small.

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